

Chemical Constituents of *Launaea nudicaulis*: C-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy of Taraxasterenes and Pseudo-Taraxasterenes*

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Chemical investigation of *Launaea nudicaulis* yielded β -sitosterol, its acetate and taraxasterol. ^{13}C NMR spectral analyses of taraxasteryl acetate (1b), pseudo-taraxasteryl acetate (1d) and 3β -hydroxy-30-nor-taraxasteran-20-one (2) were made and the diagnostic features are discussed.

PROMPTED by the folk-lore associated with the medicinal properties¹ of *Launaea nudicaulis* (Compositae) we have made a systematic chemical investigation of the plant. This has resulted in the isolation of a triterpenoid and two steroidal constituents, which are identified as taraxasterol, β -sitosterol and its O-acetyl derivative, respectively. The identification is based on their physical constants, spectral data and comparison with authentic samples. In view of a number of recent publications²⁻⁵ on ^{13}C nmr spectral studies on several triterpenoid systems, viz., α - and β -amyrins^{2,3}, 18,19-oleanenes⁴, lupanes⁵ and hopenes⁵, the isolation of taraxasterol from *L. nudicaulis* in fairly good yield prompted us to carry out detailed ^{13}C nmr spectral analyses of the triterpenoids of taraxasterene and pseudo-taraxasterene types. The present communication while briefly reporting the isolation of the chemical constituents of *L. nudicaulis*, primarily concerns with the results of the ^{13}C nmr spectral analyses.

The compounds studied for the purpose are the acetyl derivatives of taraxasterol (1a) and pseudo-taraxasterol (1c) and the norketone (2). Pseudo-taraxasteryl acetate (1d) was obtained by treatment of taraxasterol with sulphuric acid followed by acetylation of the product, while the norketone was prepared by the action of OsO₄ on taraxasteryl

acetate (1b) followed by periodate oxidation of the resultant 3,20,30-triol. The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts of 1b, 1d and 2 (Table 1) were based on off-resonance decoupling technique indicating substitution profile of carbon centres, functionality manipulation causing predictable shift variations, and comparison with the carbon chemical shifts of appropriate diterpenes⁶ (for rings A and B) and triterpenoids²⁻⁵, viz., α - and β -amyrins^{2,3} (for rings A and B), lupanes⁵ and hopenes⁵ (for rings A, B, C and part of D), having some commonness in the carbocyclic systems.

Comparison of the carbon chemical shifts of 1b, 1d and 2 with those of other triterpenoid systems has revealed several distinguishing features. Except the carbon atoms of rings A and B, the carbon chemical shifts of these compounds show practically very little resemblance to those of α - and β -amyrins. This is primarily due to removal of the 12,13-double bond of the amyrins, introduction of the C/D-*trans*, a change over from D/E-*cis* to D/E-*trans* stereochemistry and the structural modification of ring E. This is reflected in the change of chemical shift of C-9 (upfield shift by ~ 3 ppm) and carbons of C, D and E rings. The most significant is the extraordinary 9-11 ppm shielding of C-27, a characteristic feature also observed in 18,19-oleanenes, the lupanes⁵ and the hopenes⁵. While in 18,19-oleanenes this upfield shift of C-27 is due to the removal of β -effect by C-19 and addition of a γ -effect by C-12, in the case of 1b, 1d and 2 as well as in lupanes and hopenes this may be attributed to the addition of a γ -effect by C-18 and the enhancement of γ -effect by C-12. In fact, the carbon chemical shifts of the compounds under investigation exhibit close resemblance to those of lupanes except C-17 and most of the ring E carbon atoms. The most striking is the chemical shift of C-17 which is shielded by ~ 8.5 ppm compared to the lupanes. This may be attributed to the changed shielding parameters caused by the

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replacement of the *trans*-hydrindane system (rings D and E) of lupanes by *trans*-decalin moiety in **1b** (*trans*-octalin and a *trans*-decalone system in **1d** and **2**, respectively).

new members of the pentacyclic triterpenoids of the taraxasterane and pseudo-taraxasterane types.

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFT^a OF **1b**, **1d** AND **2**

	1b	1d	2
C-1	38.7	38.4	38.7
C-2	23.5	23.6	27.3
C-3	80.7	80.8	78.8
C-4	37.6 ^b	37.7 ^b	38.9 ^b
C-5	55.3	55.3	55.3
C-6	18.0	18.1	18.2
C-7	33.8	34.2	33.9
C-8	40.7	41.0	40.8
C-9	50.2	50.2	50.3
C-10	36.9 ^b	36.9 ^b	37.0 ^b
C-11	21.3	21.5	21.1
C-12	25.4 ^c	26.9 ^c	25.6 ^c
C-13	38.3	39.1	37.5
C-14	41.8	42.1	41.7
C-15	26.5 ^c	27.5 ^c	26.5 ^c
C-16	39.2 ^d	36.2	36.0
C-17	34.3	34.1	34.1
C-18	48.5	48.6	49.8
C-19	38.2	42.2	46.0
C-20	154.2 ^e	139.6	218.0
C-21	25.3 ^c	118.8	33.1
C-22	39.0 ^d	36.6	36.3
C-23	27.7	27.8	27.9
C-24	16.1 ^e	16.2 ^d	16.8 ^d
C-25	15.7 ^e	15.9 ^d	15.8 ^d
C-26	16.1 ^e	16.2 ^d	16.2 ^d
C-27	14.5	14.6	14.5
C-28	25.0	21.6	21.8
C-29	19.3	17.6	15.3
C-30	107.0	22.4	
-OCOCH ₃ ^f	170.5	170.6	
-OCOCH ₃ ^g	21.0	21.3	

^aThe δ values are in ppm downfield from TMS ; $\delta(\text{TMS}) = \delta(\text{CDCl}_3) + 76.9$ ppm.
b, c, d, e, Values bearing the same superscript may be interchanged.

Other differences in the chemical shifts of the carbon sites of ring E between these compounds and the lupanes are in conformity with the structural variations of this part of their molecules. The chemical shift assignments for C-29 and C-28 in **1b** are supported by functionality manipulation. Thus, replacement of the exocyclic methylene of **1b** by a C-20 carbonyl function (as in **2**), and the isomerisation of the 20,30-double bond to 20,21-position (**1d**) affect the chemical shifts of both C-29 and C-28, the latter then approaching the value of the corresponding carbon in the lupanes. The reverse assignments for these carbon sites in **1b** would demand an improbable upfield shift (~10 ppm) of C-29 in **2**. Furthermore, in view of the existence of a severe steric interaction⁷ between the 29-methyl and the 12-methylene groups, the assigned chemical shift of C-29 appears more logical than otherwise. The differences in the carbon chemical shifts of **1b** and **1d** are only formal and are in accord with those expected from double bond isomerisation.

The results of these spectral analyses thus disclosed diagnostic features which would provide a method for future ¹³C nmr spectral recognition of

Experimental

Isolation of 1a : Air-dried powdered whole plant (1 Kg) of *L. nudicaulis* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°), CHCl₃ and MeOH. Concentration of petrol extract deposited a white solid (yield 0.06%) which was filtered. The crude solid, on repeated crystallisation from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1) mixture, gave pure **1a**, m.p. 221°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 95.6$ (CHCl₃); acetate (**1b**), m.p. 239-40°. The filtrate was chromatographed over silica gel using petrol and petrol-EtOAc mixture as eluents. The petrol-EtOAc (20 : 1) eluate on evaporation yielded a further quantity (0.15 g) of **1a**. The petrol-EtOAc (10:1) eluate gave β -sitosterol acetate (yield 0.007%), m. p. 121°, crystallised also from MeOH-CHCl₃ mixture. Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) gave β -sitosterol (yield 0.01%), m.p. 136°; acetate, m.p. 121° (identical with the natural product). Chromatography of CHCl₃ and MeOH extract furnished only traces of **1a** and β -sitosterol.

Isomerisation of 1a to 1c and acetylation of 1c to 1d : **1a** (0.2 g) was dissolved in a mixture of 10% ethanolic H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and benzene (10 ml) and refluxed for 5 hr for the double bond isomerisation as reported⁷ earlier. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water, extracted with ether, dried and evaporated. Repeated crystallisation of this solid (0.19 g) from MeOH-CHCl₃ gave pure **1c**, m.p. 196°; $M^+ 426$; $\delta_{ppm}^{CDCl_3}$ 1.60, 3H, s and 5.18, 1H, m ($Me-C=CH-CH_2-$). **1c** was acetylated with Ac₂O/Py in the usual manner to give **1d**, crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃, m.p. 228°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 51.8$ (CHCl₃); ν_{max}^{KBr} 1735 and 1250 (OAc) cm⁻¹.

Conversion of 1b to 2 : Following the method reported⁷ earlier for structurally similar compound, **1b** (1.9 g) dissolved in a mixture (1 : 1) of dry pyridine and CHCl₃ (100 ml) was treated⁷ with OsO₄ (1 g) and the solution was kept at 20° for 7 days. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the dark brown mass was treated⁷ with benzene (45 ml), MeOH (45 ml) and a mixture of KOH (10.5 g) and mannitol (10.5 g) in EtOH (45 ml) and water (28 ml), and refluxed for 3 hr. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure left a residue which was diluted with water, extracted with ether and dried. The ether extract, on evaporation, gave a solid which was chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol-EtOAc (1 : 1) eluate gave a crude mass of triol (0.75 g) which was dissolved in EtOH (320 ml) and treated⁷ with a solution of sodium *meta*-periodate (0.55 g) in water (5.5 ml). The mixture was kept at 20° for 16 hr. EtOH was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water, extracted with ether, dried and evaporated. The solid (0.47 g), on repeated crystallisation from petrol-EtOAc, gave pure **2**, m.p. 260° (Found : C, 81.2 ; H, 11.24. C₂₉H₄₈O₂ requires C, 81.30 ; H, 11.21%). $\nu_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 3380 (OH) and 1700

(>C=O) cm^{-1} ; $\delta_{\text{ppm}}^{\text{CDC}13}$ 3.15, 1H, m ($-\overset{|}{\text{CH}}-\text{OH}$),
 2.40, 3H, m ($\text{Me}-\overset{|}{\text{CH}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 1.1, 3H,
 d, J 7 Hz ($\text{Me}-\overset{|}{\text{CH}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$), 0.71-1.0 ($6-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$);
 m/e (relative abundance): 428 (M^+ , 17.5), 410 (63.5), 395 (40.9), 367 (25.1), 341 (10.7), 328 (29.3), 259 (10.8), 207 (41), 189 (100), 136 (77.8), 135 (76.3), 123 (60.6), 121 (64.7), 109 (55.5), 95 (77.9), 81 (65.9), 69 (61.8), 55 (55.3) and 43 (45.7).

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